

WHITE PAPER

Ecosystem Technologies

January 2025

An SRA 6 White Paper

**EUROPEAN TECHNOLOGY
PLATFORM FOR HIGH
PERFORMANCE COMPUTING**

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Executive Summary

This is a white paper released as part of the ETP4HPC's Strategic Research Agenda 6.

“Pushed by massive deployments of compute and storage capabilities at the edge, we require a new system design to accommodate the ecosystem change to be expected in the coming decades (environmental and technological) and horizontally integrate the different actors. The new demands and challenges that combine data and compute, distributed across the continuum, and the maintenance and resource efficiencies, are pushing for drastically increased software and hardware sustainability. Furthermore, the need to provide high-level cybersecurity is profoundly changing the game. Efficiency and resilience will have to reach levels never achieved so far, while taking into account the intrinsic distributed and heterogeneous nature of the continuum. In addition, the question of dealing with such high volumes of data needs to be faced, and quality versus quantity will become unavoidable. These considerations will spread over all components. Long-lifetime hardware devices will have to be reconfigurable, modular, and self-aware in order to be operational over extended periods. Algorithm efficiency will need to be drastically pushed up (e.g. more efficient AI). Management and deployment of large-scale application workflows will have to be adapted or invented. Network protocols will have to offer better control over the data logistics, etc.”

This paragraph from SRA4 (2019) has not lost any relevance over the past 5 years. The awareness for a multi-faceted, holistic approach in the design of complex IT compute and data infrastructure though has increased. Several initiatives were formed, and projects launched focusing on a better understanding of the very diverse IT domains forming this continuum.

This SRA6 White Paper differs in structure from the others which have focussed on specific layers of the HPC stack.

First, it explains the term “compute and data continuum” and the context in which “Ecosystem Technologies” is used in this SRA. HPC-centric technology is only one of several technical domains in this continuum. Secondly it introduces initiatives which focus on a deeper understanding of the technical implications of such a continuum. Then two examples of European and international lighthouse projects with significant challenges in the area of ecosystem technologies are presented. Finally, the R&I requirements identified to master these challenges are listed.

Glossary of acronyms

5G: fifth generation of telecommunication systems

6G: sixth generation of telecommunication systems

ACL: Access Control List

CERN: [European Organization for Nuclear Research](#)

ECMWF: [European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts](#)

EGI: The EGI Foundation offers a federation and management platform that enables service providers to harmonise interfaces and connect to a common hub

ESFRI: European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures

HEP: High-Energy Physics

HL-LHC: [High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider](#)

R&I: Research and Innovation

SKAO: Square Kilometre Array Observatory

SOC: Security Operations Centre

TCI: [TransContinuum Initiative](#)

Introduction

High-Performance Computing (HPC) is increasingly becoming a cornerstone within a diverse and interconnected technological ecosystem. Traditionally used for simulations on data and models locally defined, or for research and scientific discovery, HPC is now expanding its reach and integrating seamlessly with the broader landscape of information technology. This evolving ecosystem spans from the Internet of Things (IoT), where vast networks of smart devices generate and collect data, to conventional server infrastructures that manage and process this data. Powerful HPC systems perform complex analyses and simulations, for example constantly updating digital twins of physical systems, using data coming from the real world.

Figure 1 illustrates the interconnected and dynamic nature of modern computational ecosystems. It begins with the capture of real-time data through various field-deployed sensors. These sensors gather essential environmental and operational data, forming the foundational layer of the data processing pipeline. Once captured, this data undergoes pre-processing at the edge or on-premises, leveraging edge computing to reduce latency and bandwidth requirements. Edge computing allows for quick and efficient initial analyses by processing data close to its source before it is sent to more centralized systems for further consolidation and analysis.

Figure 1: the wheel of the Continuum of Computing¹

The next stage involves the consolidation of pre-processed data in data lakes in the cloud as well as locally. These centralized storage solutions enable extensive data aggregation and

management, providing scalable storage and computational resources necessary for handling large datasets. The cloud infrastructure supports the massive scale of data generated

¹ Original version of Figure 1 courtesy of HIPEAC

by modern sensors and prepares it for high-level processing.

High-performance computing (HPC) systems then utilize this consolidated data to perform complex simulations and create digital twins. These digital twins are virtual models that accurately replicate physical systems, allowing for analyses and predictions. HPC's computational power makes it possible to execute tasks that would be impractical on less powerful systems, driving forward scientific and industrial advancements. Cloud technologies are most efficient to perform a large number of mid-size and small tasks while HPC are most efficient in running very large tasks that require a large number of computing cores.

Additionally, the ecosystem integrates artificial intelligence (AI), sophisticated algorithms, and robust cybersecurity measures. AI enhances data analysis capabilities while advanced algorithms optimize processing tasks. AI is also used to speed up the simulation process and to make it more resource efficient. Cybersecurity ensures the integrity and privacy of data throughout the process and communication. This comprehensive approach ensures that data is not only processed efficiently but also securely.

Challenges along the continuum must be addressed at the global system level rather than through a collection of local optimizations, since improving one aspect of one given component or sub-system impacts other parts of the continuum and may impede operations². Moreover, jointly developing sub-systems, considering their complex interactions is the best way to maximize the overall efficiency. A truly multidisciplinary and trans-sectoral co-design effort is therefore needed, as well as a shaping strategy including governance and policies, covering many domains including access to energy, Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) containment, supply chain management, predictive maintenance strategies, etc. beyond the many technologies required to implement these facilities (artificial intelligence, cyber-security, smart sensors / IoT devices, extreme scale data transport / distribution / access & federation, etc.).

A real example of this complex continuum of computing is illustrated by the European Initiative Destination Earth, described further down in this report.

² See also ETP4HPC white paper:
<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5534464>

Federating around the continuum of computing

The TransContinuum Initiative (TCI)³

Following the observations that the continuum of computing is a reality, and that each part described in Figure 1 is represented by a different organization that only focuses on its particular domain, ETP4HPC and HiPEAC came to the

conclusion that it would be interesting to create in Europe a structure where these organizations can meet and discuss their domains in the broader context of the continuum of computing. This led to the creation of the TransContinuum Initiative.

Figure 2: The TCI logo derives from the wheel of the Continuum or Computing

The TransContinuum Initiative (TCI) is a collaborative effort among multiple European associations and projects aimed at addressing the convergence of data and computational infrastructure essential for advanced industrial and scientific applications. It seeks to foster seamless integration across various digital technologies to support complex data workflows, enhancing Europe's capacity to tackle modern challenges such as healthcare, climate change, and smart cities.

TCI really embodies the vision of a "Digital Continuum", integrating millions of computational devices across a spectrum of technologies and platforms, including IoT devices, supercomputers, cloud systems, and high-speed networks like LAN, WLAN, and 5G. This infrastructure is

crucial for efficient data processing and analysis in contemporary digital environments.

The initiative aims to eliminate silos between different IT disciplines, creating a unified approach to tackle technological challenges related to interoperability and efficient data management across diverse systems. High-performance computing (HPC) serves as the core engine driving advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), big data, IoT, and cybersecurity.⁴

³ <https://www.etp4hpc.eu/transcontinuum-initiative.html>

⁴ See also <https://ecs-org.eu/8-european-associations-and-projects-commit-to-the-trans-continuum-initiative/>

TCI focuses on five primary objectives to advance its vision:⁵

1. **Elaborate Joint Recommendations for R&D:** TCI aims to develop joint recommendations for research and development to be conducted under EU-funded work programmes. These recommendations will address challenges in the digital continuum, including technological functionality, interoperability, and standards.
2. **Engage with EU Research & Innovation Funding Entities:** The initiative seeks to actively engage with European R&I funding bodies to promote its recommendations and ensure they align with broader European strategic goals.
3. **Generate an Interdisciplinary Network:** TCI aims to foster a network of experts from both science and industry, facilitating the exchange of ideas and the formation of interdisciplinary consortia to address emerging challenges and opportunities within the digital continuum.
4. **Contribute to Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas:** The initiative contributes to various strategic documents and agendas, ensuring that interdisciplinary technical aspects are considered and that a holistic view of the digital continuum is maintained.
5. **Support Horizon Europe Missions:** TCI plans to support the Horizon Europe missions by integrating digital twin technologies and other digital solutions to address societal challenges such as climate change, healthcare, and smart cities.

TCI is a collaborative effort involving eight major European associations and projects, each contributing their expertise to create a cohesive strategy for the digital continuum. These organizations include:

- **6G-SNS** (6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association)

- **AIOTI** (Alliance of Internet Of Things Innovation)
- **BDVA** (Big Data Value Association)
- **EPoSS** (European Platform on Smart Systems Integration)
- **ECISO** (European Cybersecurity Organisation)
- **ETP4HPC** (European Technology Platform for High-Performance Computing)
- **EU-Maths-In** (European Service Network of Mathematics for Industry and Innovation)
- **HiPEAC** (High Performance, Edge And Cloud computing)

These collaborations aim to leverage each organization's strengths to address the comprehensive challenges of the digital continuum, fostering innovation and driving advancements in various technological domains.

TCI's efforts included in-depth analyses of digital twin use cases to identify implementation challenges and research and innovation priorities for the coming years. The initiative emphasizes the development of reconfigurable, modular, and self-aware hardware devices to ensure sustainability and efficiency in data-rich environments.

Moreover, TCI engages in consultancy projects like Destination Earth (DestinE). TCI brings a wealth of expertise in high-performance computing (HPC), cloud computing, high-bandwidth networking, IoT, edge computing, AI, mathematical methods, and cybersecurity to the DestinE project. TCI has been awarded to present technical recommendations to ECMWF in the context of the implementation and operation of the DestinE engine on EuroHPC systems. These recommendations, written up in 6 white papers focus on (1) Federation of Compute and Data resources, (2) Data streaming, (3) IoT and Networking, (4) Cybersecurity, (5) Mathematical Methods & Algorithms, and (6) an analysis of gaps between the outcome of the white papers and current work-programmes and calls issued by EUROHPC and Horizon Europe.

⁵ <https://www.etp4hpc.eu/transcontinuum-initiative.html>

This work outlines the digital technologies needed to ensure the success of DestinE's digital twins, and exemplifies how interdisciplinary efforts can drive significant advancements in digital infrastructure.^{6 7}

The Computing Continuum Initiative⁸

To further increase the exchanges of the organizations on the topic of their roadmaps and various Strategic Research (and Innovation) Agendas, another informal collaborative structure was created, including the TCI partners mentioned above, called "The Computing Continuum Initiative".

The Computing Continuum Initiative is a collaborative platform that aims to drive innovation and alignment within Europe's computing systems. This initiative focuses on advancing research, technology development, and strategic partnerships to bolster Europe's digital infrastructure and support its technological sovereignty. The Computing Continuum Initiative is committed to fostering technological progress through a unified approach that brings together academia and industry organizations. Similar to TCI, the initiative's vision is to create a seamless and integrated computing environment that spans from edge devices to cloud data centers, encompassing high-performance computing (HPC), artificial intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), and big data analytics. Currently, it comprises:

- **6G Smart Networks and Services (6G SNS):** The 6G SNS project is pivotal in driving Europe's leadership in 5G and 6G networks. As a public-private partnership, it shapes a comprehensive research and innovation roadmap, emphasizing technology sovereignty and facilitating the widespread deployment of 5G.
- **Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation (AIOTI):** AIOTI aims to lead advancements in IoT and edge computing by promoting research, innovation, and standardization. This alliance focuses on deploying converging technologies to benefit European businesses and society.
- **Big Data Value Association (BDVA):** BDVA plays a crucial role in Europe's data-driven digital transformation. It focuses on data spaces, AI, data protection, and the convergence of HPC, data, and AI. BDVA develops strategic roadmaps and guidelines to foster an ecosystem that prioritizes data interoperability, scalability, and sustainability.
- **Chips Joint Undertaking:** The Chips JU is a significant initiative aimed at redefining the European semiconductor industry. It focuses on research, design, and innovation in intelligent digital systems, enhancing Europe's position in the semiconductor landscape.
- **Destination Earth:** This collaborative effort aims to build a digital twin of the Earth, focusing on climate change and extreme weather events. It leverages Europe's HPC and AI capacities for high-resolution modeling to predict and adapt to climate impacts, improving responses to natural disasters.
- **Eclipse Foundation:** The Eclipse Foundation supports the development of commercially-friendly open-source software. It hosts projects that build an open development platform with extensible frameworks, tools, and runtime libraries for software development and management across its lifecycle.
- **European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO):** ECSO is dedicated to building and federating the European cybersecurity ecosystem. It involves large companies, SMEs, research centers, universities, and public

⁶ <https://stories.ecmwf.int/etp4hpc-to-support-destination-earths-technology-agenda-and-roadmap/index.html>

⁷ <https://destine.ecmwf.int/news/etp4hpc-to-support-ecmwfs-technology-agenda-for-destination-earth/>

⁸ <https://www.hipeac.net/news/7047/leading-the-way-for-the-computing-continuum-at-hipeac-2024/>

administrations to enhance cybersecurity capabilities across Europe.

- **European Technology Platform for High-Performance Computing (ETP4HPC):** ETP4HPC promotes European HPC research and innovation. It aims to maximize the economic and societal benefits of HPC for science, industry, and citizens by proposing research priorities and program contents in HPC technology and usage.
- **EU-MATHS-IN:** This network connects national networks and organizations across Europe to develop the interface between mathematics and industry, promoting the application of mathematical research to solve industrial challenges.
- **FIWARE Foundation:** FIWARE focuses on developing an open-source software platform standard to facilitate the creation of smart applications. It aims to build a sustainable ecosystem that supports free and accessible technology for various sectors.
- **High Performance, Edge And Cloud computing (HiPEAC):** HiPEAC supports the computing continuum ecosystem, integrating computing, connectivity, AI, and cybersecurity.
- **Inside Industry Association:** This association strives to position Europe as a leader in intelligent digital systems by fostering a multidisciplinary network that promotes technology exchange, strategic R&I agendas, and large innovation initiatives.
- **Networked European Software and Services Initiative (NESSI):** NESSI is dedicated to enhancing European industry competitiveness through R&D in software, data, and digital services. It emphasizes AI-assisted software engineering as a key innovation, offering solutions like AI-assisted programming and explainable software for regulatory compliance and debugging.

The TransContinuum Initiative and the Computing Continuum Initiative are complementing each other and are de facto aligned due their common stakeholders. Currently, TCI has more actions in sharing expertise of the various organizations, for example to help projects like DestinE, while the Computing Continuum Initiative, more recently, focuses on the exchanges and possible alignments between the various roadmaps, SR(!)A, etc. of its participants.

To showcase the importance of this idea of “continuum of computing” resources, we will highlight several projects or structures where this synergy of the various elements of the computing continuum is key.

Examples of projects illustrating the continuum of computing

The Spectrum project⁹

SPECTRUM unites leading European science organisations in High-Energy Physics (HEP) and radio astronomy together with e-Infrastructure providers to formulate a strategy for a European compute and data continuum. The project, coordinated by EGI Foundation, will deliver both a strategic agenda, and a technical blueprint for a European compute- and data continuum.

The amount of data gathered, shared and processed in frontier research is set to increase steeply in the coming decade, leading to unprecedented data processing, simulation and analysis needs. In particular, HEP and radio astronomy are gearing up for groundbreaking instruments, necessitating infrastructures many times larger than the current capabilities. SPECTRUM aims to facilitate the creation of an Exabyte-scale research data federation and compute continuum.

To achieve this, the project brings together European science organisations and e-Infrastructure providers to formulate a Strategic Research, Innovation, and Deployment Agenda (SRIDA), along with a technical blueprint for a European computer and data continuum. This will define the vision, overall goals, main technical and non-technical priorities, investment areas and a research, innovation and deployment roadmap for data-intensive science and infrastructures.

⁹ <https://www.spectrumproject.eu/>

Two examples of the compute- and data continuum

Destination Earth¹⁰

Destination Earth (DestinE) is an initiative launched by the European Union aimed at creating a highly accurate digital twin of the Earth. This project leverages advanced computing, data integration, and simulation technologies to model, monitor, and predict natural and human activities, with a focus on addressing environmental and societal challenges. The primary objective of Destination Earth is to develop a digital representation of the Earth that can simulate and predict natural phenomena and human impacts with unprecedented accuracy. This digital twin will integrate vast amounts of data from various sources, including satellites, ground-based sensors, and climate models, to provide real-time monitoring and predictive capabilities.

¹⁰ <https://destination-earth.eu>

Figure 3: Destination Earth: the Digital Twin Engine

Besides the collection of information from weather stations, IoT devices or satellites, the key elements directly related to HPC are:

- **Digital Twin Engine:** The Digital Twin Engine (see figure 3) is the core software infrastructure of the project. It will power the digital twins, integrating real-time data with simulation models to provide continuous updates and predictions. This engine will handle the complex computational tasks required to maintain and update the digital twins.
- **Data Lake:** Managed by the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT), the Data Lake will aggregate data from various sources, including the European Space Agency (ESA), Copernicus, and other environmental data repositories. It will support big data processing and provide seamless access to a comprehensive data portfolio.
- **Core Service Platform:** Implemented by ESA, the service platform will be an open, flexible, and secure cloud-based computing infrastructure. It will provide users with access to data, applications, and services related to the digital twins, enabling interactive exploration and analysis.

These building blocks are sketched in Figure 4 below. The Digital Twin Engine will run on a distributed HPC datacentre infrastructure implemented by four EuroHPC systems: LUMI (Finland), LEONARDO (Italy), MARE NOSTRUM 5 (Spain) and yet to come JUPITER (Germany).

Figure 4: Destination Earth: a simplistic view on the major building blocks

More details on the implications learned from DestinE will be exposed in the key R&I recommendation part.

Large scale infrastructures for physical sciences¹¹

The next generation of multi-science hubs such as SKAO and CERN's HL-LHC, (both ESFRI landmarks), will need to realize the complete digital continuum through a hierarchy of cyber-infrastructures, fed by science sensors in real-time at the edge (on the left side in figure 5); filtering, combining, processing and reducing these data streams in quasi real-time locally on super-computers; and generating high-level data products to be delivered to a distributed community of scientists, relying on cloud infrastructures, for analysis and science production (right side of Figure 5). At a high level these scientific

communities face the same main challenges in looking towards the implementation and exploitation of these experiments:

- Shifting to a data flow approach since data streams have to be reduced in real-time before being discarded
- Fitting development, operations, maintenance and upgrades within a restricted cost envelope for computing
- Managing a new scale of data volumes, up to the multi-Exabyte scale
- Adapting the software investment to rapidly and continually changing heterogeneous computing hardware
- Leveraging potential commonality in software tools and services across experiments and infrastructures

¹¹ source: Damien Gratadour - CNRS

Key R&I Recommendations

General observations

In general, we can state that:

- HPC will be one element in a continuum of computing, in charge of simulating very large tasks (like a digital twin of the Earth, or of industrial plants and processes) but fed with data coming from the real world. This will have a lot of implications for HPC technologies: e.g. **computing loads with hard or soft real-time requirements** for obtaining results or stream processing “on the fly”, **communication** of data in and out with all the **security** related aspects, **authentication** of systems connected to the HPC engine, etc. (see the section on Destination Earth).
- **New types of data intensive workloads, (such as AI)** that will be linked with more “classical” HPC workloads: That could have an impact on the hardware architecture as the requirements are not the same for AI and classical HPC:
 - AI needs a lot of fast memory,
 - “aggregation” of resources or coupling nodes into virtual “supernodes” - similar to what Nvidia is doing by virtualizing several GPUs together to form a super-GPU with few PB of memory accessible from the nodes¹² (kind of “remote memory pooling”) with all the implications in terms of number of NICs, latency, coherency and bandwidth,
 - simulation needs FP64 (or more), while AI could work with far lower precision, down to FP4 for example,
 - the move from “data storage” to “data lakes”.

¹² See the section “System Hardware Components” of this SRIA

We look at the below two major areas in some more detail:

- Destination Earth - the DE_380 project
- Large scale infrastructures for physical sciences (SKA-O and CERN’s HL-LHC)

Destination Earth – DE_380 project results

In September 2022, ECMWF and TCI (led by ETP4HPC) started a cooperation (the DE_380 project)¹³ on specific technology topics surrounding Destination Earth, the European Union’s initiative to create a digital twin of the Earth System. ETP4HPC, together with its partners from the TransContinuum Initiative (TCI) has generated a technical agenda for DestinE focusing on these domains:

- D380.3.3.1_Federation of Compute and Data resources
- D380.3.3.2_Data Streaming
- D380.3.3.3_IoT and Networking
- D380.3.3.4_Cyber Security
- D380.3.3.5_Mathematical Methods & Algorithms

The technical agenda is composed of five white papers. In addition, an analysis was performed comparing recommendations made in these papers with currently available work programs (EuroHPC, 6 G-SNS and Horizon Europe). Recommendations for R&I actions in the next four years and beyond were identified and are presented here:

¹³ <https://stories.ecmwf.int/etp4hpc-to-support-destination-earths-technology-agenda-and-roadmap/index.html>

Recommendations with impact in the next 1-2 years

Near-term recommendations for potential solutions or options for solutions implementable within 2025 and 2026:

- Develop a centralized role account management system for all EuroHPC centres involved in DestinE, which will allow seamless user identity management across different platforms and centres. The main challenge will be that each centre will keep their existing account management systems, so this will be both a technological and political challenge.
- Leverage existing, permission or ACL-based systems to provide data access control on the basis of role accounts.
- Establish a security operations centre (SOC) to enhance threat detection and response capabilities.
- Establish a CoE (Centre of Excellence) to help with portability and interoperability between entities.
- Initiate the creation and standardization of service deployment practices and container platform agreements among EuroHPC centres to facilitate streamlined and secure service operations.
- Design and implement a hybrid model for streaming data that combines push-based and pull-based systems to optimize for varying data volumes and ensure real-time processing capabilities.
- Transition towards post-quantum cryptographic methods to future-proof security measures.
- Begin implementing data compression techniques and test 5G connectivity enhancements to optimize the interfacing between GEANT and 5G networks, ensuring efficient data transmission and reduced energy consumption.

Recommendations with impact in 3-4 years

Recommendations for solutions or options for solutions implementable in 2027-2028:

- Implement a comprehensive user management framework that handles complex data access policies, ensuring compliance and secure multi-domain interactions. Providing means for fine-grained, usage-based data access control.
- Evolve the service deployment strategies to integrate with emerging EuroHPC JU federated solutions, enhancing cross-centre orchestration and scheduling capabilities.
- Strengthen data governance frameworks to incorporate advanced data usage control and privacy management, aligning with emerging standards for data sovereignty.
- Integrate a common interoperable set of APIs allowing to use various accelerators. Ideally, this should be extended to edge and fog computing technologies to improve data processing speeds and efficiency where data is collected, reducing the load on central systems, while maintaining interoperability and thus reducing the development cost.
- Continue the development of hybrid AI/classical models that strike the right balance between physics-based constraints and machine learning flexibility, ensuring consistency with physical laws, and addressing issues of model interpretability and robustness.
- Advance the development of AI-driven optimization tools for real-time resource allocation, help for optimization and predictions of the mode of operation, and system efficiency within high-performance computing environments.
- Develop robust data quality assurance frameworks, including service monitoring to ensure the reliability and accuracy of data and services used.

- Extend the testing and optimization of next-generation network interfaces to accommodate increasing volumes of data and integrate advanced connectivity solutions such as satellite and 5G advanced deployments.
- Develop predictive security models that utilize AI to anticipate and mitigate potential cyber threats before they materialize.
- Explore the integration of (XR - eXtended Reality) applications to enhance user interactions and data visualization techniques in environmental and climate modelling.

Longer term outlook (Beyond 4 years)

As we look into the future beyond the immediate and medium-term recommendations, the focus should shift towards establishing sustainable, innovative, and highly integrated solutions that anticipate technological advancements and evolving user needs. The key areas to consider are:

- Use the latest developments in artificial intelligence used for robust hybrid models consistent with physical laws, allowing interpretability or verification, increasing the performance of data processing at multiscale levels for improving weather forecasting¹⁴.
- Foster the development of next-generation federated systems that not only connect but also intelligently manage resources across a wide range of computational environments. Implement fully automated (AI-driven) service deployment, orchestration, and scheduling systems that take into account data location and transfer, and dynamically adapt to changing computational loads and priorities across global networks. Create self-optimizing streaming architectures that predict and adapt to network conditions in real-time, ensuring optimal data fidelity and throughput.

- Establish robust, decentralized identity and access management systems (for example using distributed ledger technologies) to enhance security and privacy while ensuring seamless user experiences across multiple platforms.
- Promote the adoption of next-generation communication technologies, such as 6G and beyond, which will facilitate ultra-reliable low latency communication (URLLC) and massive machine-type communication.
- Develop and integrate quantum-resistant cryptographic solutions to secure streaming data against future threats posed by quantum computing.
- Advance the development of AI-enhanced security operations centres that can preemptively respond to cyber threats before they impact system operations.

Large scale infrastructures for physical sciences

A science community behind SKAO and high energy physics has worked out several requirements to enable a robust, persistent, energy efficient and secure IT infrastructure for big science instruments. These requirements touch on multiple domains and again, as with DestinE, need to be tackled in a holistic approach. Here is a snapshot:

Computing performance & science return

- Scale-up the application and ensure the inherent load balancing across a heterogeneous HPC infrastructure.
- Explore opportunities to use mixed precision to enable the ability to trade accuracy for efficiency or consumed energy, and leverage emerging AI-optimised hardware for signal processing functions.

¹⁴ Of course, also other simulations like CFD would benefit. This list was created for DestinE.

- Monitor and manage resources and energy usage at fine grain across the pipeline execution to cope with various observational scenarios as well as changes in energy availability or cost.
- Build modular and cost-effective cyber-infrastructures, leveraging emerging hardware technologies to trade-off performance / accuracy / cost and power efficiency
- Adapt to heterogeneous infrastructures hosting various compute & I/O technologies.
- Foster persistent software development over time to reduce development costs beyond the initial effort and to keep software maintenance and evolution cost under control.

Towards innovative data driven approaches and the management of new scales of data volumes

- Better integration of data ingestion/processing in a single streaming process, e.g. through in-network computing.
- Development of energy efficient algorithms for fast data processing on the edge, based on compression techniques (e.g., quantization, pruning, knowledge distillation) applied at training time or after training.
- Development of common software solutions for efficient training and inference, with emphasis on workflow automation, reproducibility, and robustness.
- Support of end-to-end secured data workflows.
- Smart and energy efficient management of data logistics.

Outlook: Industrial immersive technologies

Of course, not all the R&I requirements presented above call for investments in future EuroHPC work-programmes. But, if the domain of HPC as discipline to solve complex problems wants to stay vital and connected with a dramatically changing technology landscape, an end-to-end horizontal approach to solving inter-related technical issues in a compute- and data continuum needs to be put into action.

At the same time significant advancements in edge computing, the deep penetration of AI in all layers of computing (be it centralized or distributed) and the increasing use of virtual realities and digital twins have enabled new use cases. This is shown in Figure 6 where Industrial environments make increasing use of so called “immersive technologies” creating a world of digital realities which allow to better control and operate complex industrial processes.¹⁵ A typical example is Nvidia’s Omniverse which federates multiple technologies and providers allowing to create realistic (in the sense of the laws of physics) virtual worlds that can be used

both to optimize industrial processes¹⁶ and to train new AIs.

What needs to be sorted out now is how the compute and data continuum we talked about in the science-centric projects, DestinE or SKAO / HL-LHC, will, in a few years from now interact with other forms of continuum like for e.g. industrial immersive physical-digital-virtual continuum. Industrial users will have to help with this analysis and evolution.

And, last but not least, one more topic should be subject of further analysis: “HPC as a service” in a compute and data continuum. As pointed out above, there are edge-centric industrial use scenarios which, in an age of heavy AI adoption, might be in need of a performant AI-training platform as part of the continuum or heavy compute intensive Digital Twins. A temporary use of “HPC as a service” might be a solution. Standards will play a significant role in the context of a good adoption rate!

¹⁵ Edge IoT Industrial Immersive Technologies and Spatial Computing Continuum, AIOTI WG Research and Innovation, 30. April 2024

¹⁶ For example, <https://blogs.nvidia.com/blog/synctwin-digital-twins-generative-ai-openusd/?nvid=nv-int-bnr-784525>

Figure 6: The concept of an industrial immersive physical-digital-virtual consortium¹⁷

¹⁷ Edge IoT Industrial Immersive Technologies and Spatial Computing Continuum, AIOTI WG Research and Innovation, 30. April 2024

Conclusions

The technical challenges associated with the compute and data continuum grow very rapidly with the increasing difficulty to master a complex, global and interrelated world. The known societal impacts due to e.g. climate change, renewable energy supply and mass transportation (to list only a few) require solutions much faster than anticipated only a few years ago. Therefore, breaking silos and interdisciplinary R&D in the IT-space at large is an absolute necessity. A necessary, but not sufficient, step forward could be taken by a series of new CSAs discussed for 2025 work programmes.

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¹⁸ hipeac.net/vision

¹⁹ <https://stories.ecmwf.int/etp4hpc-to-support-destination-earths-technology-agenda-and-road-map/index.html>

Cite as: Duranton M., Malms M., ETP4HPC SRA6 White Paper – Eco-system Technologies, 2025, Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14731389>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14731389

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